

Exploring the Affordances of Musical Practice as Research

**Kgomotso Moshugi, Yonela Mnana, Mbuso Khoza, Evans Netshivhambe,
Rui Laranjeira, and Brett Pyper (chair)**

Panel abstract. This panel draws together work by five current and/or recent graduate students of the Wits School of Arts at the University of the Witwatersrand in Johannesburg, all of which speak to the conference theme of “Performing, Engaging, Knowing.” All five projects, each introduced in concise 10-minute video sequences, entail the application of research by engaging various publics beyond academia, employing practice-based or artistic research methodologies. The musical genres covered range from indigenous vocal and/or choral forms to pre-and postcolonial transnational oceanic circulations, to jazz and contemporary art music. The respective projects explore the affordances of musical practice as research in the context of deep social engagement in the crucibles of cultural encounter and contestation on the seam between the Atlantic and Indian oceanic worlds, Southern Africa.

Kgomotso Moshugi: Re-location of a creative idea in the production of knowledge

In exploring artistic interventions aimed at change of a social and political nature, the integration of the Euro-American congregational hymn in South Africa is to be fundamentally understood as the movement of a devotional and musical cultural artefact from one set of people to another. While initially conceived in the West, its relocation locally implies not only a geographical shift but also a social, political, and cultural one, concurrently. Due to the creative agency of local Christian communities, it is to be expected that the hymn will always assume a local character embellished with cultural inflections at varying degrees, of the people who express it. Hence, congregational singing, inherently participatory, becomes a form of social knowing through which a hymn is encountered and reformed in collective and culturally nuanced ways. The local community of Seventh-day Adventists is no different. Even under conditions that are extensively instructional through musical notation and other structural impositions that undermine local agency, somehow local expressions of these hymns continue to bear permeating local qualities. For the church at large to suggest strict adherence to the singing of hymns as scripted for a Western setting is to deny agency to its constituency, the liberty to be human. My pre-occupation here is to provide advocacy and help generate tools of reflection and the ability to recognize and value this agency as a crucial foundation for localization and creativity. For example, I deconstruct the very translation of one hymn from English to a vernacular language and illustrate its complexity as a process, a position which enables the appreciation of the otherwise often unrecognized value in linguistic localization endeavors. Although my project is not fully immersed in the language and tenets of applied ethnomusicology as an artist researcher, it is my growing understanding that this study has undeniable ties with its sentiments as a discipline and practice. Inspired and informed by local Adventists as my community of cultural practice and

research, I labor to restore human dignity through the recognition of the socially embedded knowledge and cultural value against the hegemony of Western impositions. The area of hymns is but one essential manifestation of agency, existent regardless of political or social command, that I am engaging with, even as I continue to consult in various capacities within the church community towards its cultural advancement and sensibility.

Yonela Mnana: Matshikiza's King Kong re-heard: A pianistic inquiry

Todd Matshikiza, the famed Drum magazine reporter and composer of the South African hit musical of the late 1950s, King Kong, always found himself straddling multiple worlds. I am studying these by means of performed analysis of a rare, unreleased solo piano recording by the composer himself, probably dating from the end of the celebrated Sophiatown era. Drawing on my experience as a jazz pianist as a resource for research, I study such issues as the bodily emplacement that I hear in this recording. As an insider-listener and eventual beneficiary of this pianistic tradition, my research aims not only to be on the culture of South African solo jazz piano but in it. I thus see this work linking with the conference theme of practice-based approaches to (ethno)musicological research.

Evans Netshivhambe: Malende music as a cultural shield

I conducted my PhD research as a practice-based composer who used traditional music elements from the Venda culture (a culture of my own heritage), to reimagine my embodied dance practices through composition. Having had the opportunity to learn composition in a university context and having had the opportunity to apply this training through practice-based inquiry, I position my compositional voice through embodiment as a core feature in my music. I would like to highlight my position as a young black composer trained in Western classical music, who did not experience the choral hymnody trajectory most South African black composers did when undergoing their musical training in South Africa. This position is aimed at exerting my compositional voice through my cultural music. The dichotomy of inspirational sources between the black South African choral composers and one's own traditional music, performed on indigenous instruments and by traditional performers, is a reality that many young, emerging black composers of my generation face today. The challenge of using Western tools to express an embodied identity of traditional African music within one's own musical heritage poses a seemingly impossible obstacle. Applying new methodologies of characterizing African music elements within African art composition is a key component to my research endeavors.

Rui Laranjeira: Unce: A Mozambican music of Arabian influence

My research project is about a hitherto unstudied Mozambican urban music and the development of a community museum that documents it. Unce, meaning enjoyment in Swahili, is an urban music of Arabian influence which is practiced in the southern region of Mozambique, namely in Maputo, Gaza, and Inhambane. The Islamic influence on the east

coast of Africa long predated the fifteenth century, when Portuguese colonists arrived. The purpose of this paper is to initiate a discussion about the Arabic influence in Mozambique and these communities' contribution to the creation of Mozambican cultural identity, which was suppressed by both the Catholic Portuguese and the postcolonial Marxist-Leninist states. Methodologically the project involves artistic research and approaches based on applied ethnomusicology to design an exhibition that can reflect the cultural realities of this Afro-Arab community. Our purpose is to carry out transformative and socially responsible research on Unce because it is part of a community that is culturally rich and deserves to be preserved and protected.

Mbuso Khoza: Performing/Knowing Amahubo

Amahubo songs are a rare style of music and also serve as a scroll of the Zulu nation. They are associated with a time when Nguni people were in control of their destiny. In those days, each household used to have a family song called ihubo, which was used to safeguard family history and also served as a prayer for the respective families. My symposia, performances, and education work are aimed at reminding people about the importance of heritage, including the rich repository of language preserved in these songs. As such, I aim to link critical understandings of heritage with artistically informed research methods, thereby offering interventions for social and political change.

Kgomotso Moshugi is a PhD candidate, teacher, vocal arranger, and performer whose current research integrates conventional qualitative modes of inquiry with those that are artistic. As a musical arranger, he incorporates professional practice and academic research within his knowledge production endeavors. His studies include South African choral cultures, choral arranging, and politics of resistance; appropriation and intersection of cultures in post-colonialism, cultural leadership, policy, governance, and entrepreneurship; and politics of sacred and market contexts in cultural production.

Yonela Mnana is a jazz pianist, teacher, and PhD candidate in the Wits School of Arts. His research interests center on the evolution of South African jazz pianism, some of which he has studied with notable veteran musicians. He also composes songs that carry this tradition forward.

Evans Netshivhambe is a young South African composer interested in music identity through African Art composition. His PhD in African music composition, completed in the Wits School of Arts in 2019, incorporates Venda rhythmic elements into African art music and exploring new sound world through composition. He is currently a lecturer at the University of Pretoria for African music studies.

Rui Laranjeira is a Mozambican researcher, with a Master's in cultural heritage management from Flinders University in Australia. His research interests are the fields of history, urban music, cultural heritage and museum curatorship. Presently, he is working at the Higher

Institute of Arts and Culture (ISArC) in Maputo, where he is head of the Resource and Studies Centre (CER). He is a PhD student in heritage studies at the Wits School of Arts, working on the doctoral project described below.

Mbuso Khoza is an award-winning vocalist and songwriter from Eshowe in Kwa-Zulu Natal. Winner of a Best Jazz Album award in 2013, he has performed extensively in countries like Senegal, Burkina Faso, Portugal, Switzerland, France, and The Netherlands. As a researcher, he has made an in-depth study of precolonial Zulu regimental genres including amahubo, which he performs himself and has taught to a young group of singers called the KZN Heritage Ensemble. He has also instituted an annual symposium on amahubo. He is currently pursuing his cultural heritage research and activism as an MA student in the Wits School of Arts.

Brett Pyper is Head of the Wits School of Arts at the University of the Witwatersrand in Johannesburg. As a Fulbright scholar, he earned Master's degrees from Emory University (in Interdisciplinary Studies, focusing on Public Culture) and New York University (in Ethnomusicology and Popular Music Studies). He was awarded his Ph.D. on contemporary jazz culture in South Africa by NYU in 2014. He has taught arts, culture and heritage policy and management at Wits, as well as ethnomusicology and popular music studies at Wits and Rhodes Universities. From 2008-2013 he was CEO of the Klein Karoo National Arts Festival (KKNK), one of South Africa's major festivals of art, popular and vernacular culture. He serves as a mentor for The Festival Academy, a project that trains young festival managers worldwide. His research interests include South African music, the transnational circulation of cultural commodities and practices, contemporary refigurations of public culture, curating and theorizing festivals, cultural ethnographies of the South African transition post-apartheid, and sound studies within the urban humanities. He is the principal investigator for a project funded by the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation that explores arts-led research across all disciplines housed in the Wits School of Arts, prioritizing perspectives from the global South.

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